

WASTEWATER TREATMENT BY CHEMICAL METHOD
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Abstract: *During the oxidation process, toxic impurities in water are converted into non-toxic substances as a result of a chemical reaction, and they can be separated from the water. When wastewater is treated with oxidizing agents, a large amount of reagent is consumed. Therefore, this method is used when it is not possible to treat wastewater pollutants by other methods. Oxidation with ozone allows you to simultaneously decolorize water, eliminate various tastes and odors, and neutralize water. Wastewater can be cleaned of phenol, petroleum products, hydrogen sulfide, arsenic compounds, surfactants, cyanides, dyes, carcinogenic aromatic hydrocarbons, and pesticides by ozonation.*

Keywords: *Wastewater, waste, ozonation, cyanides, phenol, petroleum products, hydrogen sulfide, arsenic compounds, surfactants, dyes, carcinogenic aromatic hydrocarbons, pesticides, iron sulfate, sodium bisulfate, hydrogen, sulfur dioxide, pyrite ash.*

Introduction

Nowadays, as the population of our planet increases, the need for clean water is increasing day by day. Due to the increase in waste and wastewater, the level of pollution of water bodies is increasing. As a result, water bodies are becoming unusable. Solving this issue positively is one of the most important problems facing countries around the world. If this problem is not solved in a timely and sensible manner, the consequences will worsen day by day.

Therefore, if scientific and technical achievements are not used to protect water bodies, if the relevant regulatory bodies do not strengthen their work in this regard, and if industrial and urban wastewater treatment facilities do not work, the health of the population and the need for clean water will always be at risk.

Water plays an important role in the main processes occurring in nature, as well as in human life. In industry, water is used as a source of raw materials and energy, a coolant or heater, a solvent, an extractant, a means of transporting raw materials and materials, and for a number of other needs.

In this regard, paying great attention to the protection of the nature and water bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Supreme Council of the Republic approved the Law on State Sanitary Supervision on July 3, 1992. This law attaches great importance to the protection of the environment, water bodies, and providing the population with clean water.

Therefore, filters, coagulants, various reagents, disinfectants (chlorine, calcium chloride, ozone), and physical methods are used to improve water quality. Maintaining the taste of water depends on the choice of water sources. The smell and unpleasant taste of water are eliminated by its treatment.

The degree of harmfulness of wastewater depends on the nature and composition of pollutants (toxicity) in it. Salts of heavy metals, cyanides, phenols, hydrogen sulfide, carcinogens and other similar substances lead to high levels of toxicity and odor change of wastewater.

Therefore, ozonation of wastewater (passing O₃ gas) is of great importance. In this case, by passing ozone gas through water, wastewater can be clarified, its taste improved, odor removed and neutralized. During the ozonation process, wastewater can be cleaned of

phenols, petroleum products, H₂S, arsenic compounds, PAV (surfactants), cyanides, dyes, carcinogenic aromatic hydrocarbons, pesticides.

Ozone is an allotropic modification of oxygen, a light purple, highly toxic gas. Its specific odor has a concentration of $1 \cdot 10^6$. It is located in the upper stratosphere of the atmosphere, molecular weight — 48, density — 2.154 g/l. Pure ozone is explosive (in industry it is obtained from oxygen - 0.2), a highly toxic compound. The maximum permissible concentration in the air of the working zone is 0.0001 mg/m³. The neutralizing effect of ozone gas is due to its high oxidizing properties, that is, it has the ability to easily give atomic active oxygen ($O_3 = O_2 + O$). Ozone oxidizes all other metals except gold, converting them to oxide form. It decomposes very slowly in dry air. When wastewater is treated with ozone gas, organic compounds in it decompose, and bacteria die (1000 times faster than chlorine).

The solubility of ozone in water depends on the pH of the solution and the substances dissolved in it. If there are acids and neutral salts dissolved in water, ozone dissolves well. If there are alkalis in water, ozone dissolves more difficultly.

The effect of ozone can proceed in three different directions: through the action of atomic oxygen in ozone, through the complete binding of ozone to the oxidizable substance, and through the catalytic action of atomic oxygen in ozone. When ozone is passed through wastewater (dispersion), 2 main processes occur: oxidation and disinfection. At the same time, the water itself is saturated with oxygen. Ozone is supplied to wastewater in the form of an ozone-air or ozone-oxygen mixture. The ozone content in the mixture is about 3%. Now let's look at the technological scheme (Figure 1).

1 - Fig. Wastewater ozonation disinfection device:

1-mixer; 2-pump; 3-reactor; 4-collector; 5-ozonator device; 6-gas purification unit.

In this scheme, after mixing the wastewater with reagents in the 1-mixer, it is fed to the 3-reactor using the 2-pump.

Here, under the influence of ozone gas prepared in the 5-ozonator, the substances contained in the wastewater are oxidized and become harmless. The purified water is sent to the next stage through the 4-collector. The gases formed during the purification stage are neutralized in the 6-block and released into the atmosphere. In this case, the residual amount of ozone used in the purification process must also be retained.

Because ozone gas is actually a strong poisonous gas. Therefore, this gas leaving the reactor is passed through activated carbon (Fig. -2). 450 g of activated carbon is used to produce 1 kg of ozone.

Figure 2. Nozzle ozonation device.

Ozone oxidizes both inorganic and organic compounds in wastewater. For example, with iron and manganese compounds, the following reactions occur:

The oxidation of hydrogen sulfide proceeds as follows:

The oxidation of ammonia proceeds as follows:

This produces nitric acid:

Reduction method: Wastewater treatment by the reduction method is used when there are rapidly reducible substances in the water. This method is widely used to separate mercury, chromium, arsenic from wastewater, and they are separated from water using settling, filtration or flotation methods.

If organic compounds of mercury are found in water, the organic substance is first decomposed, then mercury cations are reduced to the metallic state. To purify wastewater from hexavalent chromium, it is first converted to trivalent based on the reduction process, and then chromium hydroxide is precipitated in an alkaline medium. Activated carbon, iron sulfate, sodium bisulfate, hydrogen, sulfur dioxide, pyrite ash, etc. are used as reducing agents. In practice, sodium hydrosulfate (bisulfite) is most often used.

This reaction occurs rapidly, and the environment is around pH=3-4. Alkaline reagents are used to precipitate trivalent chromium.

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